

Merck's Global Tax Circuit: How Intangibles Power Cross-Border Profit Shifting

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Merck & Co., the American pharmaceutical giant behind blockbuster treatments like Keytruda, has cultivated a global tax strategy every bit as sophisticated as its scientific research. At the heart of this model lies a pair of Irish subsidiaries with minimal physical assets and maximum financial firepower—complemented by a Dutch outpost that quietly houses the crown jewels.

These entities—MSD International GmbH and MSD International Business GmbH—sit quietly in Tipperary. But behind their unassuming names is a sprawling web of intellectual property rights, intercompany loans, and tax-efficient structures that have helped shift tens of billions in global profits away from high-tax jurisdictions.

Intangibles as a tax engine

Between 2021 and 2023, MSD International Business GmbH saw its intangible assets soar nearly fourfold—from \$733 million to \$2.8 billion. Over the same period, the subsidiary's revenues ballooned to \$34.2 billion, with \$8.9 billion in post-tax profits in 2023 alone, and income tax expense of over \$1 billion.

On paper, this appears aligned with Ireland's 12.5% statutory corporate tax rate. The entity reported \$1 billion in Irish tax, implying an effective rate of 11.8%. But the structure behind it is more intricate.

MSD International Business GmbH is technically a "foreign" entity of another company of the same name, likely domiciled in Switzerland—which maintains favourable tax treaties with Ireland. This design allows Merck to book profits in Ireland while potentially attributing taxing rights elsewhere, further compressing its global tax bill.

Ireland most likely serves as the primary booking centre, economic income may have flowed onward—likely through Switzerland or other jurisdictions offering preferential tax regimes, IP amortisation relief, or generous intercompany deduction treatment.

The Dutch patent warehouse

Crucially, Ireland is not Merck's primary IP hub. While only 800 patents are registered with its Irish subsidiaries, nearly 15,000 patents are housed in the Netherlands—specifically through Merck Sharp & Dohme International Services B.V., a Dutch subsidiary based in Haarlem.

Despite reporting over \$16 billion in annual revenue and holding over \$10 billion in current assets, the Dutch entity has no reported intangible assets on its books. Its net income for 2023 was a meagre \$1.3 million—suggesting that while it handles substantial sales and logistics, the associated profits are stripped out through service arrangements or intercompany fees. In effect, the Dutch arm operates as a high-volume conduit, housing IP rights without showing the associated profit.

This further supports the notion that Merck's intellectual property is centrally owned in the U.S., but economically exploited across multiple tax-advantaged jurisdictions—with the Netherlands and Ireland acting as key nodes in a tax-efficient network. It also reinforces the point that intellectual property can be sliced and diced into different intangible assets on different balance sheets.

Critically, Merck consistently generates more profit overseas than it does in the U.S., yet pays a fraction of the tax. This long-standing gap reflects the deliberate rerouting of profits through lower-tax jurisdictions while shielding them from full U.S. taxation.

An architecture built to shift

Merck's profit-shifting (or what legal-accountants prefer to call "profit allocation") strategy rests on interlocking mechanisms:

- **Intellectual property transfers:** Patents and trademarks are potentially moved to Ireland or the Netherlands and licensed back to group affiliates, generating royalty income in low-tax centres.
- **Intra-group financing:** Internal loans between affiliates generate interest deductions in high-tax jurisdictions and income in low-tax ones.
- **Indefinite reinvestment:** Previously, foreign profits were declared as "indefinitely reinvested," allowing Merck to defer U.S. tax on those earnings.
- **Preferential regimes:** Merck has disclosed the use of tax holidays in countries like Singapore and Ireland, and benefits from special rules around IP amortisation and interest deductions.

A U.S.-made strategy

While Ireland and the Netherlands offer the legal scaffolding, the true enabler of Merck's tax architecture is the U.S. tax code. Despite reforms under the 2017 Tax Cuts and Jobs Act—including GILTI and FDII—U.S. law continues to reward the offshoring of intangible assets and the deferral of foreign income.

In effect, the intellectual property (and most of the jobs and sales/revenue) originates in the U.S., but the rights to economically exploit it are allocated across borders, ensuring the associated profits are taxed lightly, if at all.

Notably, Merck employs more than 75,000 people globally. Of these, approximately 29,000 are in the USA, 3,000 are based in Ireland, 6,000 in the Netherlands, and 1,000 in Switzerland—jurisdictions that play an outsized role in its tax strategy.

Final thoughts

It goes without saying that Merck's tax and profit-shifting model is perfectly legal. It is also highly efficient from the perspective of capitalism. By spreading its intellectual property rights across Ireland, the Netherlands, and Switzerland—while relying on a permissive U.S. tax framework—it has built a global profit-shifting circuit that turns intangible assets into enduring tax savings.

Until that architecture is dismantled by U.S. legislative reform, the engine will keep humming, and capitalist democracy will be undermined.

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